

REFLECTION OF THE IMAGE OF NATURE IN THE TRANSLATION OF THE NOVEL "TERRIBLE TEHRAN".

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Abstract. In this article, The famous novel "Terrible Tehran" and its translations into Uzbek language were analyzed and examined through examples of landscape images. The purpose of writing this article is to analyze the translations of works translated from modern Persian literature into Uzbek language, to study the achievements and shortcomings of the translator, his skills, by comparing the original and translated texts. Analytical, descriptive and comparative methods were used in this article.

Key words: image, landscape, translation skill, nature image, comparison, artistic work.

INTRODUCTION

There are many types and varieties of translation: translation of literary works, translation of scientific and technical literature, translation of political and journalistic materials, translation of official office documents, translation of films. Based on this, according to the nature of the translation, it is divided into literary, scientific, journalistic and official translation. Among them, literary translation stands out for its difficulty, complexity, and high requirements. That's why, literary translation stands out from other types of translation due to its uniqueness and the special skills it requires from the translator.

The uniqueness of literary translation is determined, on the one hand, by its place among other types of translation, and, on the other hand, by its connection with the original literary work. Literary translation does not simply function as a communicative (social link) with language: the word here appears as the "basic element" of literature, that is, in its aesthetic function. Between the starting point and the result of translation work lies a complex process of "re-expression" of life, which is fixed in the figurative fabric of the translated work¹. Therefore, the problems of literary translation lie in the field of art and are subject to its specific laws. From this it is clear that literary translation is a literary process that occurs in the process of re-creation of an existing literary work in a certain language in another language.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Landscape imagery is one of the most important factors that determine the skill of both the writer and the translator. The process of translating a work of art from one language to another requires great skill from the translator. Because every work of art reflects an image. The translator revives the lines of imagery created by the writer. In the translation process, the translator is required to translate skillfully, preserving the image of the character portrait, the landscape, the lifestyle of the heroes of the work, and their national traditions. Otherwise, the nationality of the work and the style of the writer will not be preserved.

Landscape (fr. paysage - place, country) - an important component of artistic reality created in a literary work, a depiction of the open space (closed space - interior) in which events take place. Traditionally, when we say landscape, we mean the depiction of nature. Landscape includes not only nature, but also the depiction of things created by man. In this sense, for example, the depiction of an alley or a city street is also a landscape, although they are not depictions of nature, but depictions of a place. The writer can describe the landscape in detail, stopping the development of events, or provide details related to it throughout the events. Landscape is also widely used as a means of revealing the psyche of the hero. In this case, the depiction of the place can either harmonize with the psyche of the character or serve as a contrasting background for it. The landscape, conveyed through the psyche of the hero, can be a means of describing his current state².

The beauty of the morning nature of Tehran in the novel "Terrible Tehran" is beautifully reflected in the translation, as can be seen in the following excerpt:

Original:

صبح زود پاییزیست. آفتاب ساعتی است در صحنه ی آسمان بالا آمده در اثر بارانی که شب گذشته باریده هوا لطافت خاصی دارد. گاهگاه باد سرد ملایمی میوزد در چنین ساعتی جمعی از مردم تهران مدتی پیش از خواب جسته و آماده کار شده بودند و بعضی از اهالی شهر تازه بیدار شده و از جای برمیخاست و بالاخره برخی دیگر از ساکنین پایتخت همچنان در بستر نرم خود در خواب ناز فرورفته بودند. [تهران مخوف، ۳۲۹]

Translation:

Ertalab quyosh allaqachon ko'tarilgan, havo tongda yoqqan salgina yomg'irdan keyin juda musaffo, ora-sira kishi ruhini erkalaydigan mayin shabada esmoqda edi.

Tehron aholisining ko'pchiligi uyqudan uyg'ongan, ba'zisi uyg'onmoqda, bir qismi bo'lsa hali shirin uyquda. [QT,262]

As you can see from the above passage, the passage was translated with some abbreviations. For example, the original text mentions that it is autumn and also uses a figurative analogy of the sunrise, but the translator did not reflect this in the translation. آفتاب ساعتی است در صحنه ی آسمان بالا آمده the author translated the sunrise depicted in the sentence with a simple sentence. As a result, the beauty of the nature image given in the original lost its charm in the translation. It is clear from the author's description that he chose the words in a very beautiful way and skillfully used them in the image. However, this beauty was somewhat blurred in the translation. If the above passage were translated as follows, the beauty of the original would have been preserved, at least to some extent:

“Kuz faslining erta tonglaridan biri. Kecha tundagi yomg‘irdan so‘ng mana necha soatlarki osmon sahnasida ko‘tarilgan quyosh o‘zgacha latofat bilan nur sochar, goh-goh kishi ruhini erkalaydigan mayin shabada esardi. Bu soatda Tehron aholisining ko‘pchiligi uyqudan uyg‘onib, ishga tushib ketgan, ba‘zilari endigina uyqudan turgan, va qolganlari yumshoqqina to‘shaklarida shirin uyquda uxlab yotishardi”.

From the above passage, it is no exaggeration to say that the writer likens the sky to a stage and the sun to an actor shining on that stage. The translator simply translated it as “the sun had already risen in the morning.” However, it is worth noting that the translator translated the sentence “occasionally a gentle breeze blew that caressed one’s soul” very beautifully. The writer expressed it in a very simple way, as “a gentle breeze blew.” The depiction of nature is considered one of the most important factors that demonstrate the artist's artistic skills. Because in the depiction of landscapes, the artist's skill in using words and his attitude to the space captured in his pen are revealed³. That is, scenes of nature help the reader feel the state of the hero of the work, and gain ideas about his lifestyle and life.

Now let's analyze the following passage, which contains another image of nature:

Original:

شش ماه گذشت.

شب بهاریست، نسیم سردی که باقی مانده ی لشکر زمستان بود میوزید. شاخه های درختان که هنوز بی بهره از برگهای سبز و زیبا بود. بسان مردان فقیری که پوشاکی در زمستان ندارند. لخت و برهنه اندام خود را نمایان ساخته و در اثر وزش باد سرد میلرزید. آب رودخانه که در آن فصل فزونی داشت در مسیر ناهموارش به تندی روان بود و هر بار که به سنگهای بسترش برمیخورد صدای ترسناکی را در آن سکوت

شب بلند میساخت. صدای دیگری که گوش فقط برای هم آوازی باغرش آب رودخانه بلند شده بود به گوش
میرسید. [تهران مخوف، ۴۶۱-۴۶۰]

Translation:

Olti oy o'tdi.

...yil avvalbahorning salqin bir kechasi, sovuq shabada dov-daraxtlarning yangi chiqqan barglarini tebratar edi. Soylar toshgan, pishqirib oqmoqda bo'lgan suv toshlarga urilib, ko'pirar edi. Suv shaldiroq yig'loqi ovozi bilan kecha tinchligini buzardi. [QT,348]

In the above, the translator omitted the similes used by the author. Some images were shortened in the translation. For example, the author described the cold breeze left behind by the winter as if it were a cold wind left behind by the army of winter, in a sentence with a special tone and simile, but the translator omitted this in the translation and gave it a slightly different way. In general, the author described the landscape in the above passage in a very figurative and rich way. However, the translator rounded off and shortened the sentences, and omitted parts rich in imagery. It would have been more appropriate if the nature image described by the author had been translated as follows:

“Olti oy o'tdi. Bahor kechalarining biri... qishning lashkarlari qoldirib ketgan sovuq shabadalar esar, yashillik va go'zallikdan bebahra qolgan daraxt shoxlarini tebratar, qishki qalin kiyimi yo'q bechora kambag'allar kabi yalang'och tanasi ko'rinib turar va sovuq shamolda dag'-dag' qaltirar edi. Daryo suvi to'lib ketganidan pishqirib oqar va har safar toshdan toshga urilgan mahal tun sukunatida daxshatli ovoz chiqarardi. Bu ovoz bilan birga eshitilib turadigan yana bir ovoz daryo suvining ko'tarishi edi”.

In the translation process, replacing original words with target language alternatives, avoiding syntax rules or formalism, paying little attention to the author's style and artistic concept of the work, and resorting to free translation often leads to incomplete expression of sentences⁴.

The depiction of nature in works of art is also one of the most important elements that determine the essence of a work of art. Because it determines how creative the translator is in the work and how effectively he or she uses the means of artistic depiction. For this reason, the depiction of nature in a work of art is an integral part of the work. Let's analyze another landscape depiction:

Original:

هوا بی اندازه سرد بود و باد زننده ای که غالباً پیش آمد برف سنگینی است سخت میوزید زمین در اثر بارانی که چندین شب پی در پی باریده بود پوشیده از گل و لای شده و بصورت منجلابی درآمده بود ابر تیره ای

آسمان را پوشانیده بود و بخوبی احساس میشد همینکه سردی هوا کمی فزونتر شود برف سنگینی افتادن آغاز خواهد کرد.

تاریکی کاملی حکمفرما بود و در آن بیابان پهناور کوچکترین روشنایی به چشم نمیخورد و فقط دو فانوس کم نوری در آن صحنه ی ظلمت در پیش و عقب سر عده ای از مردم تکان میخورد. [تهران مخوف، ۱۷۵]

Translation:

Kun juda ham sovuq edi. Hamisha qor yog'ishidan xabar beradigan izg'irin qora sovuq esardi. To'rt kun surunkasiga yoqqan yomg'ir yerni ko'pchitib yuborgan. Osmonni qora bulutlar qoplab olgan, qor yog'ishi kutilardi.

Sahro zim-ziyo, hech qayerda yilt etgan yorug'lik ko'rinmaydi. Faqat yo'lda ikki xira fonus yog'dusi ko'zga tashlanardi, biri oldinda, ikkinchisi bir guruh odamlar ortida. [QT,495]

The description of nature is given with certain hints to create an imagination in the reader before an important event occurs in the work. For example, in the novel "The Terrible Tehran", the writer often does not immediately proceed to the development of events, but first describes the place, nature, and weather where the event takes place, gradually adapting the reader to the process. In the above description, the writer also tells the above passage in his own language before describing the difficulties experienced by the main character Farrukh. Gradually, he enters into a sad story about Farrukh's experiences and the painful days he went through. Here, it can be said that the translator was able to preserve the image in its entirety. In this image, the translator, without shortening or adding anything, expressed the sentences as fluently as a writer, and this was his achievement. The translator even translated sentences such as "the bitter black cold" and "the constant rain that fell on the land" into Uzbek, conveying their rhythm. The translator also causes the reader to imagine the country through the image of nature. Therefore, it is important to deliver the translation correctly.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in the translation of nature images, many reductions were encountered. In addition, the translator simplified the imagery, similes, and animations used by the writer in the translation or completely removed them. The recreated landscape and portrait images were translated in some places with a free approach. This caused the translator to deviate somewhat from the writer's style. The translator is considered the most skillful writer, poet, and translator of his time. In some places, he tried to convey the translation to readers based on the capabilities and mentality of the Uzbek language, and he succeeded.

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